

WELLNESS EXERCISE AND THE STAGES OF ITS IMPLEMENTATION

Ikromjon Yuldashov, PhD,
Fergana State University,
Uzbekistan, Fergana city

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7526376>

Abstract: One of the main tools in the formation of a harmoniously developed generation is physical culture and sports. Because physical education and sports play an important role in the growth and health of young people. A healthy person develops self-confidence, perseverance, skills and qualities to complete the work he started.

Keywords: fitness, training, harmoniously developed generation, physical education, sports, human health, physical training, sports psychology.

ОЗДОРОВИТЕЛЬНОЕ УПРАЖНЕНИЕ И ЭТАПЫ ЕГО ВЫПОЛНЕНИЯ

Аннотация: Одним из главных инструментов формирования гармонично развитого поколения является физическая культура и спорт. Потому что физическое воспитание и спорт играют важную роль в росте и здоровье молодых людей. Здоровый человек развивает уверенность в себе, настойчивость, навыки и качества, необходимые для завершения начатой им работы.

Ключевые слова: фитнес, тренировка, гармонично развитое поколение, физическое воспитание, спорт, здоровье человека, физическая культура, спортивная психология.

INTRODUCTION

The lifestyle of people, their knowledge of sanitation, their ability to apply this knowledge in daily life and adhere to it strictly, their conscious attitude to their bodies and bodies, their attitude to their health are the most important conditions in health. These elements are factors that prolong health, physical and mental activity, longevity, longevity. In other words, the health of each individual depends primarily on his lifestyle, his conscious approach to these elements of life. In this regard, it is important to know that on the basis of a healthy lifestyle, all the factors present in the environment can affect the body, and to be able to effectively use these factors for their own health.

RESEARCH MATERIALS AND METHODOLOGY

It has been known for a long time that educated people have brought up young men and women to be beautiful in every way, and to have enviable stature when they see them. It is seen as a symbol of human health, strength, mental and spiritual maturity, has become a work of art by artists and sculptors and is displayed as a level of perfection of the human body, and sculptures created with unparalleled taste in art museums around the world continue to fascinate the audience.

Today, one of the main directions of the ideology of Uzbekistan is that a person's face, body, actions and behavior, as well as what he does should be in accordance with his perfection. Our country, which has brought up many great people in the world, is determined to bring up children who will rise to the level of greatness in the future, to introduce an education that will raise all citizens to the level of true perfection.

As a result of health training, the body not only increases strength, but also expands its thinking capabilities. Physical and mental maturity is endless, boundless, and giving it a slow or fast pace depends on everyone's aspiration, diligence, patience, will. There are processes that are important for the comprehensive development of sports and the further popularization of important

aspects of training. The main focus on sports and its popularity is formed on the basis of human responsibility to society from time immemorial.

It is known that the field that forms the social essence of a person in accordance with the needs of society is called the system of public education, and the person who implements it is called a teacher. From time immemorial, attention has been paid to the personal social qualities of teachers, and the requirements for teachers have become more sophisticated and complex, based on the requirements of each era.

In contrast to the careful development of the methodological development of the lesson, which encourages the teacher to work effectively, educational technology is focused on student activities, which serves to create the necessary conditions for independent learning of teaching materials, taking into account the individual and collaborative activities of students. The rapid development of science, engineering, production and technology has opened up new prospects for development in all spheres of society. Mankind's centuries-old experience in the construction of the state and society has led to the establishment of advanced approaches to the regulation of social relations on the basis of new approaches. At the same time, the social life of the Republic is rapidly flowing information and covering a wide range.

One of the most pressing issues facing the education system is the rapid receipt of information, its analysis, processing, theoretical generalization, summarization and delivery to the student. The introduction of pedagogical technology in the educational process serves to positively address the above-mentioned problem. Therefore, it is necessary to make certain changes in the organization of the teaching process, including the principles of improving the narrative of teaching materials. At the same time, the introduction and use of modern information technologies in the educational process are the most effective ways to achieve this goal.

At the same time, special attention is paid to physical culture and "Peace of Heart", which is one of its important stages. This is evidenced by the fact that the main task of young athletes is to pay attention to peace of mind. Sports training is a pedagogical phenomenon, a specialized process of physical education, directly aimed at achieving high sports results using a system of exercise techniques. It is important to note that from the point of view of pedagogy, sport is not a single goal, but a means of education, health and preparation for life.

Objectives of sports training: the requirements of health promotion and spiritual education, the harmonious development of the individual in all respects; mastering sports techniques and tactics; development of physical, mental and volitional qualities specific to the chosen sport, acquisition of practical and theoretical knowledge in the field of sports hygiene and self-control. During the training, not only high skills, but also health, development of physical qualities, hard work and acquisition of vital skills necessary for the defense of the Motherland are solved.

RESEARCH RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

We have described one of the simplest means of fitness training to achieve physical fitness, a vital movement - a healthy lifestyle physical culture exercise that should be considered when using walking: simple walking is done by moving most of the muscles in the human body and it affects all internal organs. The positive effect was proven before the XV century. As a result of walking or other purposeful movements, the tissues in our body, the connections between the organs of our body are activated, the fluid in the myriad large and small tubes, and with them the interstitial exchange of substances, takes place rapidly; improves the supply of cells with nutrients and building materials needed to create new tissue; the valves of the tissues, which for some reason are closed, move the stagnant organs.

Walking is the simplest and most beneficial means of maintaining a healthy body. Walking as much as possible is beneficial for all ages, but it is better to get used to walking a lot from a young age.

Walking puts a load on most muscles of the human body because the whole body shakes when one leg is lifted and the body shifts its center of gravity. The longer such shakes last, the more the body's resistance to movement increases. The increased normative volume of mental and physical labor creates the basis for longevity. By studying the secret of the longevity of people who have seen longevity, it has been proven that they walk more in the open air than others, and are in constant motion. It is important to choose and adhere to the norm of physical activity of fitness training.

The devastating effects of overtraining have been observed in middle-aged people, even those who have not yet reached puberty, with insufficient levels of movement readiness.

CONCLUSION

This means that everyone should exercise to the best of their ability, with the amount of physical load the body is accustomed to doing, which is a guarantee of physical maturity. The basis of the theory of fitness training is the recommendation to increase the load norm slightly after feeling the ease of performance compared to the period when the exercise was performed, and their full mastery by the trainee.

REFERENCES:

1. R.Salomov., M.M.Ruzioxunova. Theory and methods of physical education. Study guide. Tashkent, 1995
2. Mehmonov, R., & Parpiev, O. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL REQUIREMENTS FOR PHYSICAL EDUCATION TEACHERS. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (5), 758-761.
3. Mehmonov, R., & Parpiev, O. (2020). THE PROCESSES OF ORGANIZATION OF GENERAL AND SPECIAL TRAINING OF ATHLETES. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5), 38-40.
4. Abdurakhmonov, S. K. (2021). The Importance Of A Healthy Lifestyle In Achieving Physical Perfection. *The American Journal of Applied sciences*, 3(03), 42-47.
5. Yuldashev, I. A. (2020). PEDAGOGICAL BASES OF FORMATION OF SOCIAL ACTIVITY IN PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES. *Теория и практика современной науки*, (5), 67-69.
6. Tuxtanzarov, I. U., & Maxmutaliev, A. M. (2020). SOCIO-PEDAGOGICAL FUNCTION OF SPORT IN THE SPIRITUAL PERFECTION OF YOUTH. *Scientific Bulletin of Namangan State University*, 2(1), 367-372.
7. Tuxtanzarov, I. U., & Maxmutaliyev, A. M. (2020). SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL PROBLEMS OF WRESTLING DEVELOPMENT. *Theoretical & Applied Science*, (1), 781-785.
8. Yuldashev, I., & Toshboltaeva, N. I. (2020). ANALYSIS OF PERSONALITY TRAITS IN ATHLETE ACTIVITIES. In *Психологическое здоровье населения как важный фактор обеспечения процветания общества* (pp. 72-74).
9. Ummatqulov, T. (2022). INSON SOG'LOM BO'LISHIDA VALEOLOGIYA FANINING AHAMIYATI. *Eurasian Journal of Social Sciences, Philosophy and Culture*, 2(12), 80-88.
10. Mukhidinov, A., & Tillaev, S. (2022). NATIONAL SPORTS GAMES IN THE NEIGHBORHOOD THE IMPORTANCE OF ESTABLISHMENT. *INTERNATIONAL*

JOURNAL OF RESEARCH IN COMMERCE, IT, ENGINEERING AND SOCIAL SCIENCES
ISSN: 2349-7793 Impact Factor: 6.876, 16(3), 83-86.

11. Yuldashov, I., Umaralievich, K. U., Goynazarov, G., & Abdurakhmonov, S. (2021). Innovative development strategy in the field of sports and the basics of its organization. *Asian Journal of Research in Social Sciences and Humanities*, 11(11), 48-53.

12. Yuldashov, I., Parpiev, O., Makhmutaliev, A., Tukhtanazarov, I., & Umaralievich, K. U. (2021). Pedagogical bases of formation of physical culture and social culture in Youth. *Asian Journal of Multidimensional Research*, 10(11), 54-58.

13. Ilxomjonovich, I. I., Tolanovich, Y. T., & Baxodirovna, H. B. (2021). Physical Education In The Structure Of Professional Education. *The American Journal of Social Science and Education Innovations*, 3(03), 226-229.

14. Bahodirovna X. B., Ilxomjonovich I. I. THE USE OF RHYTHMIC GYMNASTICS IN THE PHYSICAL EDUCATION OF SCHOOLCHILDREN ON THE EXAMPLE OF THE CITY OF FERGANA //International Journal of Pedagogics. – 2022. – Т. 2. – №. 05. – С. 9-12.

15. Bobojonov, N. O. Z. I. M. J. O. N., & Madoripov, O. Y. B. E. K. Bo ‘lajak mutaxassislarining kasbiy-amaliy jismoniy tayyorgarligi. *Студенческий вестник учредители: Общество с ограниченной ответственностью «Интернаука»*, 74-75.

16. Nozimjon, B. (2022). THE IMPORTANCE OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF PHYSICAL QUALITIES IN THE MOTION OF GAMES. *Involta Scientific Journal*, 1(7), 37-43.